

Cycloids old and new

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The cycloid generated by a flatly rolling unit circle is defined parametrically as **[1]**

$$\begin{aligned}x(t) &= t - \sin(t) \\y(t) &= 1 - \cos(t) = x'(t)\end{aligned}$$

The cycloid offers a visual solution to Kepler's famous orbital equation $M = E - e \sin(E)$ **[2]**.

Now, the steps to derive a Cartesian form of the cycloid are included here for reference.

The ordinate expression can be recast as

$$\cos^{-1}(1 - y(t)) = t$$

while doubling and squaring the ordinate $y(t)$ give

$$\begin{aligned}2y(t) &= 2 - 2\cos(t) \\y^2(t) &= 1 - 2\cos(t) + \cos^2(t)\end{aligned}$$

so by subtraction

$$2y(t) - y^2(t) = 1 - \cos^2(t) = \sin^2(t)$$

Square roots here lead formally to

$$(2y(t) - y^2(t))^{1/2} = \sin(t)$$

so now the two components (in boldface red) that make up the abscissa $x(t)$ are in view; thus

$$x(t) = t - \sin(t) = \cos^{-1}(1 - y(t)) - (2y(t) - y^2(t))^{1/2}$$

or what is the same

$$\cos^{-1}(1 - y(t)) = x(t) + (2y(t) - y^2(t))^{1/2}$$

from which it follows by taking cosines of both sides and some transposition that

$$y(t) + \cos(x(t) + (2y(t) - y^2(t))^{1/2}) = 1$$

an admittedly odd-looking expression.

One arch of the cycloid ($x(t)$ vs. $y(t)$) is shown below, for $0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$; t is sampled as $0:.001:2*\pi$.

The red dot indicates where $x(t) = y(t)$ beyond the origin, estimated by Newton iteration

$$t_{n+1} = t_n - f(t_n)/f'(t_n)$$

on the function

$$f(t) = x(t) - y(t) = t - \sin(t) - 1 + \cos(t)$$

with derivative

$$f'(t) = 1 - \cos(t) - \sin(t)$$

and initial guess of $t_0 = 2.5$, converged in OCTAVE after four iterations:

$$t_0 \cong 2.412011143913525; \text{ and indeed } x(t_0) = y(t_0) \cong 1.745453415573421 \cong 5\pi/9.$$

Now, unlike sines and cosines, $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ are not orthogonal over a 2π cycle. Indeed

$$(x(t), y(t)) = \int_0^{2\pi} x(t)y(t)dt = 2\pi^2 \cong 19.73920880217872$$

using trigonometric identities and integration by parts; the OCTAVE code

```
% (x,y) integral
xy_int=@(t) (t-sin(t)).*(1-cos(t));
integral(xy_int,0,2*pi)
```

also confirmed this result numerically.

An orthogonal complement to $\mathbf{x}(t)$ can still be derived from the Gram-Schmidt procedure; thus

$$z(t) = y(t) - [(x(t), y(t))/(x(t), x(t))]x(t) = y(t) - kx(t)$$

Let's work the constant k out.

$$\text{From above } (x(t), y(t)) = 2\pi^2$$

Next

$$(x(t), x(t)) = \int_0^{2\pi} x(t)^2 dt = (8/3)\pi^3 + 5\pi \cong 98.39136774874848$$

confirmed with the OCTAVE commands

```
% (x,x) integral
xx_int=@(t) (t-sin(t)).^2;
integral(xx_int,0,2*pi)
```

Therefore

$$k = 6\pi/(8\pi^2 + 15) \cong 0.200619315025528$$

The resulting new cycloid is expressed parametrically as

$$x(t) = t - \sin(t)$$

$$z(t) = y(t) - kx(t) = 1 - \cos(t) - k(t - \sin(t))$$

One arch of this new curve is plotted below (blue), overlaid on the usual cycloid (red); what oval rolled down the incline to generate this new cycloid? It seems as if the old was swung around a vertical axis through the origin to generate the new; an optical illusion perhaps.

The incline has angle $\tan^{-1}(|z(2\pi)|/2\pi) \cong 0.197990984081904$ rad, or $\cong 11.34404776953498$ deg. The path-length is $(4\pi^2 + z(2\pi)^2)^{1/2} \cong 6.408381174790154$, thus a bit more than 2π .

The area of this new cycloid is derived from the usual integral

$$A = \int_0^{2\pi} z(t) dx = \int_0^{2\pi} z(t) x'(t) dt = \int_0^{2\pi} (y(t)^2 - kx(t)y(t)) dt$$

$$= 3\pi - 2k\pi^2 \cong 5.464711411730418$$

obviously much smaller than 3π for the conventional cycloid. The OCTAVE commands are below.

```
% Area
y_sq=@(t) (1-cos(t)).^2;
kxy=@(t) k*(t-sin(t)).*(1-cos(t));
area=@(t) y_sq(t)-kxy(t);
integral(area,0,2*pi)
```

As for the cycloid arc length, the integral is

$$L = \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{x'(t)^2 + z'(t)^2} dt = \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{y(t)^2 + (\sin(t) - k(1 - \cos(t)))^2} dt$$

Here numerical integration simplifies the computations; the commands are

```
% Arc length
dx_sq=@(t) (1-cos(t)).^2;
dz_sq=@(t) (sin(t)-k*(1-cos(t))).^2;
arc=@(t) sqrt(dx_sq(t)+dz_sq(t));
integral(arc,0,2*pi)
```

so $L \cong 8.085535714908991$, actually slightly longer than the usual cycloid, where $L = 8$.

Next, let's see if $x(t)$ and $z(t)$ also agree elsewhere beyond the origin; Newton iteration using

$$f(t) = x(t) - z(t) = (1 + k)(t - \sin(t)) - 1 + \cos(t)$$

with derivative

$$f'(t) = (1 + k)(1 - \cos(t)) - \sin(t)$$

and the same initial guess of $t_0 = 2.5$, again converged quickly towards $t_0 \cong 2.120771320705602$; and of course $x(t_0) = z(t_0) \cong 1.268233728549122$.

Now, an orthogonal complement to $\mathbf{y}(t)$ can also be derived using the Gram-Schmidt process; thus

$$w(t) = x(t) - [(x(t), y(t)) / (y(t), y(t))] y(t) = x(t) - qy(t)$$

From above

$$(x(t), y(t)) = 2\pi^2$$

while

$$(y(t), y(t)) = 3\pi$$

hence $q = (2/3)\pi$. Yet another cycloid can thus be defined parametrically as

$$\begin{aligned} w(t) &= x(t) - qy(t) = t - \sin(t) - q(1 - \cos(t)) \\ y(t) &= 1 - \cos(t) \end{aligned}$$

with $w(t)$ serving now as a new abscissa; a plot of one arch is shown below.

It would be hard to conceive of a rolling oval generating such a distorted curve. Its area and arc-length provide some surprises; first, for the area

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_0^{2\pi} y(t) dw = \int_0^{2\pi} y(t) w'(t) dt = \int_0^{2\pi} (y(t)x'(t) - qy(t)y'(t)) dt = \\ &= \int_0^{2\pi} (y(t)^2 - qy(t)\sin(t)) dt = \int_0^{2\pi} (y(t)^2) dt = 3\pi \end{aligned}$$

thus identical with the classical cycloid. However, the arc-length integral

$$L = \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{w'(t)^2 + y'(t)^2} dt = \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{(1 - \cos(t) - q\sin(t))^2 + \sin^2 t} dt$$

and the OCTAVE commands

```
% Arc length
dw_sq=@(t) (1-cos(t)-q*sin(t)).^2;
dy_sq=@(t) sin(t).^2;
arc=@(t) sqrt(dw_sq(t)+dy_sq(t));
integral(arc,0,2*pi)
```

yield $L = 11.28917148216004$, thus considerably longer than the usual cycloid; reasonable, though, given the stretched nature of this arc.

The general arc for a rolling circle is the trochoid **[3]**, with parametric representation

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= at - b\sin(t) \\ y(t) &= a - b\cos(t) \end{aligned}$$

Let's derive the Cartesian form, emulating the steps for the cycloid.

The ordinate expression can be recast as

$$\cos^{-1}((a - y(t))/b) = t, \text{ so}$$

$$\mathbf{a\cos^{-1}((a - y(t))/b) = at}$$

while doubling the ordinate gives

$$2y(t) = 2a - 2b\cos(t), \text{ so}$$

$$2ay(t) = 2a^2 - 2ab\cos(t)$$

Now square the ordinate to get

$$y^2(t) = a^2 - 2ab\cos(t) + b^2\cos^2(t)$$

or what is the same

$$y^2(t) = a^2 - 2ab\cos(t) + b^2(1 - \sin^2(t))$$

Subtraction, cancellation and simplification yield

$$\begin{aligned} 2ay(t) - y^2(t) &= 2a^2 - 2ab\cos(t) - \{a^2 - 2ab\cos(t) + b^2(1 - \sin^2(t))\} = \\ &= a^2 - b^2 + b^2\sin^2(t) \end{aligned}$$

which implies

$$2ay(t) - y^2(t) - a^2 + b^2 = b^2\sin^2(t)$$

Square roots now lead formally to

$$(2ay(t) - y^2(t) - a^2 + b^2)^{1/2} = b\sin(t)$$

Once again the two components (in boldface red) that make up the abscissa $x(t)$ are in view. The final steps are:

$$x(t) = at - b\sin(t) = a\cos^{-1}((a - y(t))/b) - (2ay(t) - y^2(t) - a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}$$

or what is the same

$$a\cos^{-1}((a - y(t))/b) = x(t) + (2ay(t) - y^2(t) - a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}$$

or

$$\cos^{-1}((a - y(t))/b) = \{x(t) + (2ay(t) - y^2(t) - a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}\}/a$$

so after taking cosines of both sides and some transposition, the Cartesian form emerges:

$$y(t) + b\cos\{[x(t) + (2ay(t) - y^2(t) - a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}]/a\} = a$$

Finally, what might be termed **Kepler's trochoid** is

$$M(E) = M = E - e\sin(E)$$

$$M(E)' = M' = dM/dE = 1 - e\cos(E)$$

or in Cartesian form

$$M' = 1 - e\cos\{M + (2M' - M'^2 - 1 + e^2)^{1/2}\}$$

On the other hand

$$(E - M)^2 + (1 - M')^2 = e^2$$

hence

$$M' = 1 - (e^2 - (E - M)^2)^{1/2}$$

all this inviting further exploration.

References

[1] Wikipedia article on the Cycloid.

[2] P. Colwell, *Solving Kepler's Equation*, Willmann-Bell, 1993, p.20

[3] Wikipedia article on the Trochoid.